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Ecolinguistic: State of The Art Phonological Anapticsis of Javanese Lamongan and Kediri Dialect

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Abstract

The Javanese language in the East Java province exhibits diverse dialects, such as the Kediri (Mataraman) dialect and the Lamongan (Arekan) dialect, which are geographically proximate. The goal of this study is to describe the different ways that phonological sounds change when the Javanese language is spoken, as well as the different ways that anaphoric sounds change when vowel and consonant phonemes are added, such as prosthesis, epenthesis, and paragoge. The research employs a qualitative descriptive method with an ecolinguistic approach. Interviews are used for data collection and acquisition, followed by note-taking and recording as the primary data reference. The analysis results reveal 33 differences in the phonological usage of the Javanese language between the Kediri (Mataraman) dialect and the Lamongan (Arekan) dialect. The classification of anaptyctic sound changes is distinctly evident in the use of the Javanese language. The dialects, in their daily usage, demonstrate two instances of change via prosthesis, two instances via epenthesis, and three instances via paragoge. The analysis identifies ecolinguistic factors influencing the phonological changes between these two dialects. Phonological changes occur as a result of contact with other languages or dialects, population migration, and social changes within the local community. The ecolinguistic study of anaptyctic phonological changes between the Lamongan and Kediri dialects indicates the influence of geographical, environmental, social interaction, and cultural factors.

Keyword: Phonological changes; Anaptyxis; Javanese language; Sub-dialect

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INTRODUCTION

Language is a fundamental communication system used by humans for daily interaction. The structural function of language is to convey messages, thoughts, ideas, and information, enabling individuals or groups to exchange viewpoints (Bonvillain, 2019). Language adheres to a set of grammatical rules that govern the use of phrases, words, sentences, and meanings (Akmajian et al., 2017). It manifests in both spoken and written forms. Moreover, language serves a social function, transmitting knowledge and cultural heritage and shaping one's worldview and perception (Tektigul et al., 2023).

Language is an essential aspect intrinsic to human identity (Joseph, 2004). Scholars have conducted extensive research on language using various approaches. The study of language has evolved beyond mere structural analysis to include functional aspects. Other disciplines like ecology and sociology often integrate with functional language research (Guerrero et al., 2018). Ecolinguistics, an interdisciplinary field combining ecology and linguistics, examines ecological phenomena related to societal language use (Kravchenko, 2016). Ecolinguistics emerged in the 1970s, when Einar Haugen introduced the language ecology paradigm. According to Haugen (1972), a language's actual environment is its social milieu, in which language and its speakers interact. Consequently, linguistic changes, both lexical and grammatical, are interconnected with alterations in the natural and sociocultural environments (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2013).

The environmental and sociocultural aspects make language an arbitrary vocal symbol system, enabling individuals within a culture, or those familiar with a specific cultural system, to interact and communicate (Bonvillain, 2019). This suggests that communicators and recipients agree on language as a consensual symbol during interaction. Language functions as an arbitrary sound symbol to convey messages within a social group (Besnier, 1990). Typically, language is defined as a collection of words and grammatical rules used in both verbal and nonverbal communication. Every language system encompasses semantics and structures to articulate ideas, thoughts, and messages clearly and effectively. Phonology, a component of linguistics, explores speech sounds, or phonemes. Zsiga (2014) generally divides phonology into two main branches: phonemics and phonetics. Phonetics focuses on the articulation of speech sounds produced by human vocal organs, whereas phonemics investigates the functional use of sounds to differentiate meanings (Huffman, 2016). Thus, phonology encompasses the analysis of linguistic sound sequences, pronunciation errors, and phonological changes leading to semantic shifts (Ladda & Mirzana, 2022).

Phonological variations in a region are characterized by unique pronunciation traits that influence sound changes. According to Crowley (1992), linguistic change is a natural phenomenon and an integral part of human social behavior. For instance, we can classify phonological changes in Javanese dialects like Kediri (Mataraman) and Lamongan (Arekan) as anaptyxis, a process that involves inserting phonemes to enhance pronunciation. Tyasrinestu (2022) identifies three types of anaptyxis: prothesis (adding a sound at the beginning of a word), epenthesis (inserting a sound in the middle of a word), and paragoge (appending a sound at the end of a word). Dialectal diversity typically features unity within diversity and vice versa, with similar speech forms across different regions. Linguistic variations stem from historical factors and the need to sustain language usage (Akbar, 2023; Senen, 2024; Qamari; Andryrestu, 2024; Maisari, 2024). Native speakers' historical aspects influence the formation of sub-dialects. Geographic factors, migration, and historical events contribute to sub-dialect development. In East Java, for example, Javanese dialects interact across different regions within the province (Azhari, 2023; Zulkhairi, 2024; Maulana, 2020; Zikrullah, 2024; Azhari, 2024).

East Java hosts various languages, such as Madurese, Osing, and Tenggerese, alongside diverse Javanese dialects like Kediri (Mataraman) and Lamongan (Arekan). Despite the geographical proximity and historical connections between Lamongan and Kediri, significant linguistic borrowing occurs during communication. Nevertheless, speakers understand each other in their daily interactions, demonstrating inherent coherence among sub-dialects within Javanese. Numerous studies have examined phonological variations in Javanese sub-dialects and their interactions with other languages. For instance, Jayanti et al. (2021) analyzed phonological changes in fruit names across Lumajang, Malang, and Kediri dialects using a descriptive-qualitative approach, highlighting general phonological variations. Rizki Widiani (2015) focused on lexical differences in daily Javanese in Lamongan, revealing lexical variations influenced by Indonesian loanwords. Rahayu (2018) explored dialectal variations in Ngawi, analyzing phonological and lexical differences in daily interactions and mapping dialectal patterns. However, this study is mainly about how the sounds in the Kediri and Lamongan dialects are different. It sorts changes in the anaptyx into different groups to show how the

sounds are different (Cristina, 2024; Munidar, 2024; Paull, 2024; Rahmadani, 2024; Johan, 2024; Ibrahi, 2024).

This research aims to identify phonological variation in the Javanese dialects of Kediri and Lamongan, particularly anaptyxis, which includes prosthesis, epenthesis, and paragoge. The research objectives are to describe the phonological variation between Kediri and Lamongan dialects and classify anaptyxis changes within these dialects. The research offers theoretical and practical benefits. Theoretically, it contributes insights into phonological variations in Lamongan and Kediri dialects, enhancing linguistic knowledge, particularly in dialectology. It serves as a practical resource for teaching phonology and vocabulary in Lamongan and Kediri. Additionally, it benefits readers interested in contemporary language development.

METHOD

This research employs a qualitative approach with a descriptive research design to comprehend phenomena occurring within society. Descriptive qualitative research is a procedure that generates words, either written or spoken, from individuals and observable behaviors (Moleong & Edisi, 2004). This study employs a descriptive analysis approach, which involves analyzing and describing various conditions and situations related to the issue under investigation. The research methodology employed is based on Haugen's ecolinguistic approach (1972). This study adheres to the Haugenian tradition, focusing on the relationship between humans and their environment. One can observe the connection between language and environment through the differences in vocabulary used in different locations (Haugen, 1972). This research applies a social praxis model of dialogic analysis, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Source: Bang and Door (1993)

This research focuses on the social environment and community language, specifically regarding phonological phoneme changes in pronunciation as well as variations in the pronunciation of words that maintain the same meaning. The study of phonological phoneme changes is centered on Swadesh vocabulary in the Javanese dialects of Lamongan (Arekan) and Kediri (Mataraman). We analyze these changes by classifying specific words based on the phonological alterations occurring within the community. Data collection methods in this research include in-depth interviews and observation with note-taking, supplemented by recording techniques to document the data obtained from interviews with informants. In linguistic research, Sudaryanto (2015) employs the observation method, which involves observing the language use of the subjects under investigation. An interview is a direct communication activity between two or more individuals, where one person (the interviewer) asks questions and the other (the respondent) provides answers. Therefore, the note-taking observation technique is an interactive method between the researcher and respondents,

involving conversations or interviews aimed at obtaining detailed information on the topic (Sugiyono, 2016).

The observation technique, which involves listening to the informants' speech and taking notes, follows the interview method. This is one of the methods used in linguistic research to observe the language use or speech of the subjects under study (Sudaryanto, 2015). We conduct interviews with native speakers, specifically students from Trunojoyo University Madura who are native to Kediri and proficient in the Mataraman (Kediri) and Arekan (Lamongan) Javanese dialects. These face-to-face interviews with native speakers allow for the construction of meaning based on the data collected using the observation-note-taking technique. The research instrument includes an interview guide consisting of a list of 200 Swadesh vocabulary items. We organize the collected data into an analysis table with these 200 Swadesh vocabulary items, comparing the dialectal differences from interviews with informants from Kediri and Lamongan. This comparison aims to identify dialectal variations and classify the phonological changes in each Javanese dialect studied.

Data analysis involves classifying and grouping data. The data analysis technique follows the principles outlined by Miles and Huberman, which include data reduction, data analysis, and conclusion drawing (Nugrahani, 2014). We apply data reduction to the interview results, forming a table for transcription based on the dialect regions under study. The transcribed data is continuously analyzed to identify differences and similarities in speech sounds, enabling the researcher to draw conclusions. The researcher draws conclusions through the interpretation of the analysis results and data.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Findings

The research findings, presented in tabular format, will address phoneme variations within specific objects that maintain the same meaning. The second section will examine phonological changes in everyday language, presented through word classification in the Kediri (Mataraman) and Lamongan (Arekan) Javanese dialects. To understand the distribution of Javanese with its various sub-dialects, please see the map below, which illustrates the spread of Javanese across the different sub-dialects in East Java.

Figure 2: Distribution Map of Javanese Dialects in Each Region (East Java)

Information:

- Dialects (mataraman) : Ngawi, Madiun, Kediri, Magetan, Nganjuk, Pacitan, Trenggalek, Tulungagung
- Dialects (aneman) : Bojonegoro, Tuban
- Dialects (arekan) : Malang, Pasuruan, Jombang, Pasuruan, Mojokerto, Lamongan, Surabaya, Sidoarjo, Gresik
- Dialects (pandalungan) : Jember, Lumajang.
- Dialects (tengger) : Tengger
- Dialects (madura) : Bangkalan, Sampang, Pamekasan, Sumenep, Situbondo, Bondowoso.
- Dialects (osing) : Banyuwangi

The map divides the Javanese language within the province of East Java into seven dialectal regions based on its distribution. This phenomenon presents a captivating subject for exploration within each locale, particularly concerning phonological variations. It is important to look at the differences between the Kediri (Mataraman) and Lamongan (Arekan) dialects because they are used in very different ways every day, even though they are both from the same province.

Phonological Variations in the Javanese Language: Kediri Dialect and Lamongan Dialect

Here are the comparative results of the phonological variations in the everyday usage of the Javanese language between the Mataraman dialect (Kediri) and the Arekan dialect (Lamongan).

Information :

- BJDK : Language of Jawa at Kediri dialect (mataraman)
- BJDL : Language of Jawa at Lamongan dialect (arekan)
- [] : phonetics
- " : phonemes

Table 1. Variations in phonological changes in Javanese Kediri and Lamongan dialect

NO	Gloss	BJDK	BJDL
1.	'bermain'	[dolanan]	[dolan]
2.	'salak'	[sala?]	[sala?]
3.	'sirsak'	[muris]	[mures]
4.	'berhenti'	[mandeg]	[mandeg]
5.	'berdiri'	[ɲadəg]	[ɲadəg]
6.	'kemarin'	[nde? ɲi]	[winji]
7.	'berangkat'	[budhal]	[budal]
8.	'duduk'	[ɲjəŋə?]	[lonŋəh]
9.	'nanti'	[əŋko?]	[əŋko]
10.	'kembali'	[mbale?]	[bale?]
11.	'mangga'	[pələm]	[pələm]
12.	'kerbau'	[kəbho]	[kəbo]
13.	'monyet'	[kətə?]	[bədhes]
14.	'menyentuh'	[ndəmə?]	[ɲjemə?]
17.	'mengkudu'	[mənŋkudu]	[kudu]
18.	'jatuh'	[cəblə?]	[logor]
19.	'mengetahui'	[wəroh]	[əro]
20.	'blewah'	[garbis]	[garbes]
21.	'bersih'	[resi?]	[rəse?]
22.	'kambing'	[wədhos]	[wədhos]
23.	'kenapa'	[ɲapə]	[lapo]
24.	'belum'	[gəŋ]	[gorəŋ]
25.	'pulang'	[muleh]	[moleh]
26.	'labu'	[waloh]	[səko]
27.	'bagaimana'	[piye]	[kepiye]
28.	'bohong'	[ɲapusi]	[mbuju?i]
29.	'lari'	[mlayu]	[mblayu]
30.	'ayam'	[pitek]	[pete']
31.	kecil	[cilik]	[cilik]
32.	'pulang'	[muleh]	[moleh]
33.	'melihat'	[ndələ?]	[ndilə?]

Classification of Phonological Changes

Some of the Javanese dialects that go through phonological changes are the Kediri (Mataraman) dialect, the Lamongan (Arekan) dialect, and the Bojonegoro (Aneman) dialect. These dialects go through a number of phonemic changes. Based on the types of phonetic modifications they represent, such as anaptyxis, prosthesis, epenthesis, and paragoge, we can categorize these changes.

Prosthesis

Prosthesis is a form of anaptyxis involving the addition of a sound at the beginning of a word, whether it be a single syllable or more. Crowley (1992) defines prosthesis as a phonological modification that involves the addition of a sound at the word's onset. The following table illustrates examples of phonological changes:

Data 1:

Original: [utah]

Changed: [kutah] (BJDK)

The word [utah] in the Lamongan dialect (BJDL) undergoes a prosthetic change to [kutah] in the Kediri dialect (BJDK). Crowley (1992) explains that prosthesis refers to the addition of a sound at the beginning of a word. In this case, the initial consonant /k/ (a voiceless, dorso-velar plosive) is added, changing [utah] to [kutah], meaning 'spilled' in Indonesian.

Data 2:

Original: [bale?]

Changed: [mbale?] (BJDK)

The word [bale?] in BJDL undergoes a prosthetic change to [mbale?] in BJDK. According to Crowley (1992), this involves the addition of the bilabial nasal consonant /m/ at the beginning of the word, changing [bale?] to [mbale?], which means 'to return' in Indonesian.

Epenthesis

Epenthesis refers to the insertion of a sound within a word. Kridalaksana (1984) describes epenthesis as a phonological change involving the insertion of a vowel or consonant within a word. The following data demonstrate epenthetic changes:

Data 1:

Original: [goŋ]

Changed: [goroŋ] (BJDL)

The word [goŋ] in BJDK, meaning 'not yet' in Indonesian, undergoes epenthesis with the insertion of the vowel /o/ and the consonant /r/, resulting in [goroŋ] in BJDL.

Data 2:

Original: [mlayu]

Changed: [mblayu] (BJDL)

The word [mlayu] in BJDK changes to [mblayu] in BJDL through the insertion of the voiced bilabial plosive consonant /b/, creating a bilabial nasal and plosive sequence at the beginning of the word.

Paragoge

Paragoge is a phonological process that involves the addition of one or more phonemes at the end of a word. Kridalaksana (1984) defines paragoge as the addition of a sound at the end of a word. The following examples illustrate paragogic changes:

Data 1:

Original: [dolan]

Changed: [dolanan] (BJDK)

The word [dolan] in BJDL, meaning 'to play' in Indonesian, undergoes paragoge with the addition of the low unrounded vowel /a/ and the alveolar nasal consonant /n/, resulting in [dolanan] in BJDK.

Data 2:

Original: [loŋgo]

Changed: [liŋgoh] (BJDK)

The word [loŋgo] in BJDL, meaning 'to sit' in Indonesian, changes to [liŋgoh] in BJDK through the addition of the glottal fricative consonant /h/ at the word's end.

Data 3:

Original: [əŋko]

Changed: [əŋko?] (BJDK)

The word [əŋko] in BJD_L, meaning 'later' in Indonesian, experiences a paragodic change with the addition of the glottal stop /ʔ/, resulting in [əŋkoʔ] in BJD_K. By examining these phonological changes, we gain a deeper understanding of the systematic nature of sound alterations within different Javanese dialects.

Discussion

The analysis of research data reveals a consistent pattern of phonological changes between the Lamongan and Kediri dialects. The Lamongan dialect exhibits a higher incidence of anaptyxis compared to the Kediri dialect, indicating distinct phonological processes between the two dialects. The significant differences in their fundamental phonological structures suggest that the Lamongan dialect possesses a more complex or richer phonological system in terms of the number of vowel and consonant sounds employed.

The analysis identifies ecolinguistic factors influencing the phonological variations between these dialects. Phonological change patterns are a result of contact with other languages or dialects, population migration, and local social changes. These factors contribute to the phonological disparities between Lamongan and Kediri dialects. The phonological differences provide new insights into the processes of phonological change in regional languages and enhance understanding of language dynamics within geographical and social contexts.

The geographical environment plays a crucial role in shaping and developing dialects (Agow & Djou, 2024). Although Lamongan and Kediri are located within East Java, they exhibit distinct geographical characteristics. Lamongan, situated near the northern coast of Java, has an environment that is more open to external influences, including trade and immigration. This openness leads to more significant phonological variation and linguistic adaptation, including anaptyxis. In contrast, Kediri is geographically more inland, thus experiencing fewer external influences. This geographical condition fosters linguistic conservatism, resulting in fewer phonological changes compared to Lamongan.

Cultural and social identity also significantly impact language change (Engracia & Perguna, 2021). The culture in Lamongan is more receptive to change and adaptation, encouraging more phonological modifications. Speakers of the Lamongan dialect are more accepting of linguistic innovations, including anaptyxis, which become part of their cultural identity. Conversely, speakers of the Kediri dialect adhere more strictly to linguistic and cultural traditions, maintaining more traditional linguistic forms. This adherence hinders phonological change, contrasting with the dynamic nature of the Lamongan dialect.

An ecolinguistic study of anaptyxis phonological changes between the Lamongan and Kediri dialects indicates the influence of geographical environment, social interaction, and culture. Additionally, language contact and multilingualism significantly contribute to the dynamics of language change. Stronger external influences and a more adaptive culture result in more extensive linguistic changes in Lamongan compared to Kediri.

CONCLUSION

In daily communication, the use of Javanese language typically exhibits distinct dialects specific to each region. The East Java province divides the dialects geographically into seven regions. This study collects data from three areas focusing on the use of the Javanese language, specifically the Kediri (Mataraman) dialect and the Lamongan (Arekan) dialect. The study identifies several notable instances of phonetic changes, particularly in anaptyctic sound changes, categorizing them into three types: prosthesis, epenthesis, and paragoge. According to research data, there are 33 instances of phonetic variation in the use of Javanese. Among these, there are two phoneme changes in consonants and vowels for prosthesis, two data points for epenthesis changes, and three data points for sound changes in paragoge.

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